

QY8911—3, A Excellent Toughness Bismaleimide resin system As the Matrix For Advanced Composites

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ABSTRACT

The resin to be used as the matrix for composites on advanced military structures are required to satisfy the service temperature and to have greater damage tolerance to obtain higher allowable strain, meanwhile, it must be ease to make operation. QY8911—3 an excellent toughened resin system, can meet the above mentioned requirements.

Keywords: BMI, Resin System

1. INTRODUCTION

Bismaleimide (BMI) are being increasingly used as matrix resin for fiber reinforced composites because of their high temperature and fire resistance performance, low smoke and toxicity characteristics. However, the major drawback of BMI is its brittle nature which in turn results in composites with low damage tolerance. The damage tolerance of the first generation BMI system is worse even than that of Rigidite 5208 epoxy resin system. In order to overcome these serious jproblems, considerable works were done during the past years. However, some

of these modifications for BMI result in low hot/wet performance due to dramatic reduction in glass transition temperature which is even lower than that of 5208 epoxyresin system^[1]. Therefore, a successfully modified BMI should have both high temperature resistant property and good toughness performance.

According to the requirements of military aircraft and missile structures, two types of modified BMI resin systems designated as QY8911—1 and QY8911—2 have been developed. A new modified BMI system, QY8911—3, an excellently toughened resin system is being completed.

QY8911—1 has good comprehensive properties^[2]. Its toughness, hot/wet property and processibility performance are in the right compromise. Now this type of BMI system has been used on aircrafts largely. Typical composites structures are vertical fin, front fuselage and canard, etc.

QY8911—2 has excellent thermal property, good processibility and medium toughness performance, which has good thermo—oxidative stability and can work at 230°C (short beam shear strength is 59MPa—66MPa at 230°C in dry condition). This type of BMI system has been used on some kinds of missile.

Now the application trend of composites is developing toward to the large primary structures of aircraft, resulting in reducing structural weight and improving structural performance more effectually, avoiding “over—designed” resulting in non—optimum structures in terms of strength/stiffness per unit of weight.

The major component of QY8911—3 is inter—chain—extended BMI. Two kinds of inter—chain extend BMI were synthesized by ourself corresponding diamines and maleic anhydride. The QY8911—3 possesses the following characteristics:

- Excellent fracture toughness property including compression strength after impact and 90° flexure strength;
- High retention of mechanical properties at elevated temperature;
- Stability in acetone solvent;
- Low post curing temperature.

2. Experiment and results

QY8911—3 as like as QY8911—1 and QY8911—2 can ease to impregnate

carbon fibre, kevlar fibre and fibre glass for preparing relative prepreg. The Prepreg of T300/QY8911—3 has long self life and wide temperature range for cure pressure applied. The QY8911—3 prepreg can also satisfied with either bleed or non—bleed method in autoclave to obtain low void or void—free composites. It can be meet precalculated thickness requirement and required fibre in volume.

Mechanical properties of T300/QY8911—3 include ordinary items and toughness data. Prior to test, samples were inspected to determine the quality by ultrasonic c—scanning and soft x—ray. The main criteria for evaluating toughness is compression strength after impact test according the SACMA—88, it simulates damage tolerance condition in which the material subjected to impact of low energy. The results are as following.

item	test ondition	Typical value
flexural strengts	22℃/dry 150℃/dry 150℃/wet	1650 MPa 1114 MPa 810 MPa
short beam shear strengts	22℃/dry 150℃/dry 150℃/wet	114MPa 79MPa 59MPa
90°tensile strengts	22℃/dry	73.6MPa
90°flexure strengts	22℃/dry	134MPa
Compression strength after impact	22℃/dry	246MPa
Glass transition temperature		257℃

References

1. H. D. stenzenberger et. , 31st SAMPE, 1986, 920—929.
2. Zhao QuSen et. , 34th SAMPE, 1989, 2182—2193.